

Hospitality Industry's Response to Health Conscious Consumer Needs: A Survey of Star Rated Hotels in Uasin Gishu County

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Abstract

As the global emphasis on health and wellness grows, hospitality operators need to prioritize their strategies in order to better appeal to the needs of the health conscious individuals. This research project aimed to investigate the response of the hospitality industry to the evolving needs of the health conscious consumers through three specific objectives i.e. to establish types of food offered, to establish types of beverages offered, and to establish fitness and wellness services offered to health conscious consumers in hotels. The research project adopted a descriptive research survey design. Descriptive survey design provided available source of information for gaining knowledge and insight into how the hotels have responded to the needs of health conscious consumers. Primary quantitative data were gathered through questionnaires distributed to a diverse sample of hotel employees. The target population for this study was 322 employees from all the star rated hotels in Uasin Gishu County. A sample size of 99 respondents was studied from the target population using the sample frame. Quantitative data was analyzed using statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) involving frequencies and percentages. Analyzed data was presented using frequency tables. The results show that the hotels provide a wide range of healthy products and services in response to the health conscious consumer needs. In conclusion, hotels must be able to deliver on their commitment to health so as to provide the positive effects on physical, mental and emotional wellbeing of the health conscious consumers. The study recommends that an image that promotes healthy products and services is a crucial strategy for hotels in order to stay competitive in the health conscious consumer market.

Key words: Hospitality industry, Health consciousness, Food, Beverages, Wellness

Introduction

The World Health Organization defines health as a state of complete physical, mental and social wellbeing and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity (WHO, 2020). Health consciousness refers to the extent to which an individual tends to perform healthy actions. It is the inner state of a person to place particular attention to their health and value behaviors promoting their wellbeing and sustainability of the environment (Global Wellness Institute, 2020). There is a growing number of people who are seeking more balanced and healthy lifestyles as regards to what they eat, what they drink and consciousness to their general health and wellness. As a result, the needs and desires of hospitality consumers are reflected in their choice of more fulfilling and authentic products that not only offer satisfaction but that also benefit their physical, mental and spiritual wellbeing i.e. the body, mind and soul (Lehto and Lehto, 2019). For the hospitality establishments to succeed, industry operators and managers must therefore respond to the needs and desires of the growing market segment of health conscious consumers by offering products and services that satisfy such needs and promote healthy lifestyles. The major products and services include a range of healthy food, beverages, accommodation, entertainment, leisure, fitness and wellness facilities like gym, swimming, massage, games and body treatment. According to McCarthy M. Collins, Flaherty & McCarthy S. (2017), Health tourism has gradually become a common form of vacationing for the health conscious consumers as it covers a wide spectrum of leisure, fun and relaxation options that incorporates wellness and healthcare. Any form of tourism directly or indirectly associated with maintaining or enhancing an individual's well-being comes under the framework of wellness tourism. Wellness tourism is now a \$439 billion industry within the worldwide tourism industry which makes a staggering \$3.2 trillion per annum. It represents 14 percent of total global tourism spending (Global Wellness Institute, 2020).

Problem statement

While health consciousness is the inner state of a person, health conscious consumers tend to make deliberate and informed purchase decisions that encourages them to take action to promote their physical, mental and social wellbeing (Lehto & Lehto, 2019). These consumers are basically those who take great care about themselves. They have a high level of self-awareness, and enjoy a more wholesome and healthier lifestyles. With consumers increasingly focusing on diet, fitness and living a healthy lifestyle, hoteliers are being driven to adapt their strategy to better appeal to these health conscious individuals. But innovating products and services to cater for the emerging needs of the health conscious consumers is

perceived by many to be economically unviable. They consider health consciousness as a self-responsibility of the consumer rather than a holistic philosophy (Lehto & Lehto, 2019). However, hospitality providers are keen to tap into this market and focus on creating successful business brands. The challenge is how they can appeal to the health conscious consumer market without having to transform and overhaul their operations and without taking advantage of the vulnerability of the consumers by giving false assurances on the attributes of their products and services especially those grouped under the healthy concept category. Emergence of the ever increasing number of health conscious consumers affects the type of products and services offered by hospitality establishments and poses a conflict between the needs of the health conscious consumers and the products and services offered.

Research questions

- i. What are the types of food offered to health conscious consumers in hotels?
- ii. What are the types of beverages offered to health conscious consumers in hotels?
- iii. What are the fitness and wellness services offered to health conscious consumers in hotels?

Significance

In a time when consumers are looking for a more balanced and healthy lifestyles, new needs and behaviors are also reflected in their requests while in hotels. Hospitality operators have a duty of care and a responsibility to be aware of aspects of their products and services that are of concern to their consumers so that they may satisfy their needs and promote their physical, mental and spiritual wellbeing. They must take clear steps to enhance their products so as to appeal to the health conscious consumers. This study aims at filling this gap standing as a reference point on provision of products and services for the health conscious consumers. The results presented will promote knowledge of the needs of health conscious consumers and facilitate hotel managers, operators and staff to offer products and services for this emerging health conscious consumer market.

Literature review

In recent years, consumers have become more conscious of the food they eat, both at home and away from home (Ali T. & Ali J., 2020). Seeking a number of specific production and nutrient based food characteristics including locally and/or organically grown, low calorie, low sodium, fresh, organic, non GMO, etc., consumers have become much more particular

about the consumption options for the food they eat (Euromonitor, 2019). However, while the production and nutrition option variations are numerous, the overriding motivation for the consumption of such products is health concern. Health conscious consumers value personal health and are sensitive to the effects of product consumption decisions on their physical appearance as well as on their general sense of wellbeing .Accordingly, these consumers are more likely to make consumption decisions that align with this value system (Hallak, Lee & Onur, 2020).

The increasing concern for health in the marketplace has not gone unnoticed by hotel operators and managers (Lin & Wu, 2019). In acknowledgement of the value of the health-conscious consumer, hotel companies from franchises, chains to single business units have introduced new products and, in some cases, entire menus that feature health focused items. Hotel managers have moved rapidly to meet the demands of health conscious consumers, and therefore, academic research has to keep pace with this particular trend in the hotel industry to provide theoretically driven empirical evidence for important managerial decisions in the industry (Lin & Wu, 2019).

Health concern can be conceptualized as a rational, cognitively derived antecedent of the decision to consume nutritious food (Jeong, Jang, Behnke, Anderson & Day, 2019). Recent trends in the hotel industry indicate increasing health concern among consumers and, in turn, increasing interest in the health-related aspects of hotel products. As consumers have become more concerned with eating healthier healthy food consumption has increased accordingly and health conscious consumers tend to seek foods with health and nutritional benefits and to eschew dining experiences that may be detrimental to health (Jeong et al, 2019). Existing research has identified a number of reasons for the increase in health consciousness among hospitality consumers including disease prevention, weight control and personal appearance. However, while a number of specific drivers exist, the common thread is enhanced personal health and well-being (Jeong et al, 2019).

Age and gender have been linked to consumer attitudes towards purchasing healthier food and drink options, although in different ways (Landstom, Hursti, Becker & Magnusson, 2017). Some evidence suggests women are more inclined to make healthy food and drink choices, have a much higher preference for healthy products, and are more likely to purchase these regularly (Bimbo, Bonanno, Nocella, Viscecchia, Nardone & De Devitiis, 2017). Women also report more positive attitudes and a greater willingness to purchase healthy food and beverages. However, while some studies have identified that women are less inclined to pay a premium for organic food, other studies found that gender plays no role in determining

consumers' willingness to purchase premium for healthy/organic food products (Ali T. & Ali J., 2020). Thus, the different contexts in which studies are conducted (i.e., food, beverages, fitness etc.) highlight the nuances in gender differences and the need to further investigate.

In contrast to gender or age, the effects of education and socioeconomic status on consumer attitudes towards healthy food, drinks and wellness is less established. Some studies report a positive relationship between levels of education and willingness to purchase nutrient enhanced foods and drinks, while others find no significant associations. Income is found to be positively associated with acceptance of functional food and drinks in a small number of studies (Sanjay McCarthy et al, 2017).

In addition to demographic factors such as age, gender, and income, research suggests that a desire to 'feel good' about oneself can be a powerful motivator in making healthy dietary choices (Jeong et al, 2019). Consumer attitudes toward health and wellbeing has a powerful effect on purchasing behavior intentions for a wide range of product categories. For example, an individual's 'health value'—defined as the extent to which the consumer places a premium on health—is a strong predictor of purchase behaviors, particularly in the context of meals away from home. Indeed, striving to pursue a healthy lifestyle for personal health reasons is an important motivation for making dietary choices (Lehto & Lehto, 2019).

Methodology

Investment in the hotel and hospitality industry account for more than 70% of growth in the property market in Eldoret town and its environs (Uasin Gishu County government, 2022), The County therefore provided a good location for this study. The research was carried out in star rated hotel in Uasin Gishu County where information on provision of healthy food, beverage, fitness and wellness services was gathered. Uasin Gishu County has nine star rated hotels which include Boma Inn Hotel, The noble Conference Center and Hotel, Poa Place Resort, Hotel Winstar, Comfy Hotel, Cicada Hotel, Kenmosa Tourist Hotel, Starbucks Hotel and The Pearl Hotel (Tourism Regulatory Authority, 2022).

The study adopted descriptive research design. Descriptive survey research design was appropriate in this study because it fully described the various phenomena under investigation i.e. provision of healthy food, provision of healthy beverages and provision of fitness and wellness services by hotels to health conscious consumers. A descriptive survey design provided available sources of information for gaining knowledge and insight into how the hotels have responded to the needs of health conscious consumers. The target population for this study was 322 employees from all the star rated hotels in Uasin Gishu County. This was arrived at through the human resources of each hotel which provided the information to the

researcher on the number of employees each hotel has before the research is conducted. Sampling was done further by proportional random sampling which attracted a sample size of 99 respondents. The study adopted a cluster sampling approach, whereby the hotels formed clusters. All the star rated hotels within the county were sampled by use of census technique. After which simple random sampling within these clusters was chosen, the size of each group being determined through proportional allocation.

Questionnaires were used by administering to the respondents as the main data collection instruments for the primary quantitative data. Open and closed ended questionnaires were used. Questionnaires are preferred because they are easy to administer and cost and time effective. The questionnaires contained both the structured and semi- structured questions. This allowed the respondents to give their views freely without the interference from the researcher. The questionnaires were administered to the employees working in hotels within Uasin Gishu County with the researcher personally distributed the questionnaires to the respondents and collected them after a period of three weeks. Before the actual study, a pilot study was done. The questionnaires were pre-tested to a selected sample. The procedure used in pre-testing the questionnaire is similar to the actual procedure which was used in the study. This was done in order to ensure the relevance of the items for the study, gain knowledge on how to administer the instruments, and test the validity and reliability of the instruments.

The study involved quantitative data and the collected data were examined in order to make inferences through a series of operations involving editing to eliminate repetitions and inconsistencies, classification on the basis of response homogeneity and subsequent tabulation for the purpose of inter-relating the variables. Once the data was checked for completeness and readiness for analysis, it was coded according to the themes researched on. The quantitative data was analyzed using descriptive statistical techniques involving frequencies and percentages to determine concentrations. Regular analysis with comparison among questions was done using frequency analysis. This made it easier to quantify and establish the variations in the number of counts observed per variable. The researcher made use of statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) to code, tabulate and analyze the data. The data were grouped together to form categories and themes according to similarities and difference. The researcher then explored the connections between categories and themes to generate broader interpretations. The results of the study were then presented in form of well interpreted and easy to understand tables.

Results and discussions

From the findings, 80% of respondents indicated that they provided fresh food, 72% low sodium, 69.3% organic, 66.7% low fat, 60% low calorie and 42% added nutrients. Others include locally sourced/ produced food, non GMO, and low cholesterol at 26.7% as shown in table 4. Majority of respondents further showed that the hotels provided fresh, low sodium, organic, low fat and low calorie food.

Type of food	Frequency (n)	Percentage (n/75)
Low fat	50	66.7
Fresh	60	80
Organic	52	69.3
Low calorie	45	60
Low sodium	54	72
Added nutrients	32	42.7
Others	20	26.7

Table 1: Types of healthy food provided

Source: Researcher (2022)

As shown in table 5, 85.3% of the respondents indicated that the hotels provide fresh juices, 64% low sugar, 46.7% low alcohol, 40% herbal teas, 37.3% decaffeinated beverages and 33.3% beverages with added nutrients. Others are smoothies, low fat/ fat free milks at 29.3%. This implies that the hotels provided healthy beverages, and majority are fresh juices and low sugar.

Type of beverage	Frequency (n)	Percentage (n/75)
Low sugar	48	64
Fresh juices	64	85.3
Added nutrients	25	33.3
Herbal teas	30	40
Decaffeinated	28	37.3
Low alcohol	35	46.7
Others	22	29.3

Table 2: Types of healthy beverages provided

Source: Researcher (2022)

According to the findings, 86.7% of the respondents indicated that the hotels provide gym services, 80% swimming pool, 44% massage, 37.4% body treatment, 32% games and 27.7% fun activities as shown in table 6. Other fitness and wellness services include meditation, yoga and outdoor recreation activities at 33.3%. The implication of this finding is that the hotels provided fitness and wellness facilities mostly gym and swimming. However, massage, body treatment, games, fun activities other services were provided at almost equal percentage of between 26% and 44%.

Type of fitness and wellness services	Frequency (n)	(Percentage n/75)
Gym	65	86.7
Swimming	60	80
Games	24	32
Massage	33	44
Body treatment	28	37.3
Fun activities	20	26.7
Others	25	33.3

Table 3: Types of fitness and wellness services provided

Source: Researcher (2022)

Hotels are increasingly incorporating healthy food and beverage options into their menus. This includes offering fresh fruits, vegetables, whole grains, lean proteins and plant based alternatives. Additionally hotels may provide organic, gluten free and allergen friendly choices to accommodate specific dietary preferences (Renzo, Gualtieri & Pivari, 2020). Filieri, Antonetti & De Angelis (2020) posit that to promote physical wellbeing, many hotels feature fitness centers equipped with state of the art exercise equipment, yoga studios, swimming pools and sports courts. These facilities allow guests to maintain exercise routines and engage in various physical activities during their stay.

Conclusion

The findings from the study show that the hotels provide a wide range of healthy products and services in response to the health conscious consumer needs i.e. healthy food, healthy beverages, and fitness and wellness services. Most popular healthy foods provided are fresh

food, low sodium, organic, low fat, low calorie and foods with added nutrients e.g. fortified foods. Others healthy foods provided are locally sourced or produced, non-GMO, and low cholesterol. Popular healthy beverages provided are fresh juices and low sugar beverages. Others are low alcohol beverages, herbal teas, decaffeinated beverages, beverages with added nutrients e.g. probiotics, smoothies, low fat and fat free milks. According to the findings, gym services and swimming are the most popular fitness and wellness services provided. Other fitness and wellness services include meditation, yoga and outdoor recreation activities.

Majority of these health conscious consumers are midrange spenders in their middle to old age with an almost equal balance between males and females. The results further suggest that health conscious consumers purchase healthy products and services because of their health concern that has direct positive effect on their physical wellbeing i.e. personal health, physical appearance and concern about weight, mental wellbeing i.e. good value for money and appropriate level of service, and emotional wellbeing i.e. giving them pleasure, sense of joy and making them happy. In this regard therefore, it was easy for the researcher to establish how the hotel sector has responded to the need of health conscious consumers because of the employees' good level of awareness of their needs.

From a theoretical standpoint, these results contribute an extension of hotel consumer behavior. The values associated with living a healthy lifestyle are demonstrated as both a direct and indirect antecedent of consumers' intentions to purchase healthy products and services. The present study can be utilized by hotel managers and operators as the beginning of a more holistic framework for the assessment of the relationship between health conscious consumer behavior and their personal values in the marketplace. This research therefore contribute an account of physical wellbeing, mental wellbeing and emotional wellbeing of health conscious consumers as it promotes an all-inclusive hotel patronage and scaling up of healthy food, healthy beverages, and health and wellness products and services range. As the findings suggest, a hotel that provides a wide range of healthy products and services will no doubt capture the health conscious consumer market.

It is important to note that health-related needs of the health conscious consumers should be carefully managed. Hotels must be able to deliver on their commitment to health. If the service experience does not match the expectations of the marketplace as communicated by the hotel, then the positive effects on physical wellbeing, mental wellbeing and emotional wellbeing of the health conscious consumers in the present research may not be realized. In fact, while the present research explicitly addresses the needs of health conscious consumers, it is quite possible that in cases where such needs are not met, the effect of health concern on

experience evaluation may actually be negative. Finally, consumer interest in healthy product options is already relatively high and appears to be increasing in the hotel sector. To turn this trend into revenue increases, hotel operators, managers and marketers will need to continue to deliver health conscious consumers physical, mental and emotional wellbeing during the customer experience.

Recommendations

This research indicates that when a full range of healthy products and services are available in hotels, consumers who value healthy living will have a more positive response to the service encounter. To stay competitive in the health conscious consumer market, developing a healthy image i.e. an image that promotes health is likely to be a crucial strategy. More hotels should continue to include healthy options on their offerings because not only is it important to ensure that healthy products are available, but also it is equally important to ensure that these options are a part of the brand and not merely an afterthought at the bottom of the menu.

One of the main concerns of health conscious consumers is the level of awareness of staff on their needs. Hotels should prioritize skilling, reskilling and upskilling of their staff with the current trends in healthy products and their service delivery. They should also ensure that staff follow proper laid down protocols and standards because an image that promotes health is a very crucial strategy for hotels in order to stay competitive in the health conscious consumer market. Finally, the hotels should communicate their healthy products and services offerings clearly to the customers. This will help build trust and confidence in the hotel's ability to provide such healthy products and services.

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